

Teaching Skills and Competency of Teacher: A Study

Dr. Ranjit Kr. Das

Asstt. Professor, Deptt. Of Education, Fakiragram College, Fakiragram Kokrajhar (Btr) Assam, India

Author Email– ranjitkrdas907@gmail.com

Abstract— Teaching is the mother of all professions. Teaching is the complex art of guiding students through a variety of selected experiences towards the attainment of appropriate teaching –learning goals. Good teaching is the result of hard work and many effort. It is a vocation filled with the excitement of helping children , discover themselves and the full range of their capabilities. For teaching, competency is necessary. Competency in planning the lesson, presentation of the lesson, ending or closing the teaching, evaluation of his students capabilities, managing the class and maintenance of discipline. Teaching competency of a teacher refers to the set of knowledge, abilities, and beliefs of teacher possesses and brings to the teaching situation. Teaching is a complex phenomenon, comprising several teaching skills. It is a set of component skills for the realization of a specified set of instructional objectives. Teaching skills are specific instructional activities and procedures that a teacher may use in his classroom. Teachers’ competence, sensitivity and motivation as the determinant factor for the quality and extent of learners’ achievement. In a way, the quality and standard of education in a country depends on how it manages its teachers’ professional development. The quality of education depends upon the quality of teachers and quality of teachers depends upon the skills they have received. No education program can be successful without proper education of teachers. Without good teachers even the best of systems is bound to fail. With good teachers, even the defects of a system can be largely overcome. The need is to acquire the best possible skills by teachers that they can contribute in raising the overall standard of education. Through this paper the author highlighted various teaching skills and competency, which are very important in teaching –learning process.

Keywords- Teaching , Competency, Knowledge, Quality, Teachers skill.

I. INTRODUCTION

The education system of India has shown enormous growth since independence. Quality education is a global demand today. And quality of teachers very much decides the quality of any education system. In any education system , teachers play the role of pivots upon which the entire system hangs.(Omorghie2006 and Mishra 2015) In raising students achievement, teachers expertise is one of the most significant factors. In this age of science and technology enormous competition and knowledge explosions, teaching skills and personal competency of the teacher is highly emphasis given huge demand in professional and job markets. Every profession demands certain specific skills and competence on the part of its practitioners. If one believes that teaching is profession, one should demonstrate certain skills and competence, which can instill learning of the students and help them, achieve their goal successfully. To promote quality teaching in the classroom , it is essential to develop the professional competencies of teachers. The teaching competency is an overall assessment of the performance of the teacher in a classroom situation on the criteria of knowledge of the subject matter, methods and techniques of teaching, art of questioning, use of teaching aids, pupils participation, teachers personality, rapport with the classroom, management and clarity of objectives. The teacher is the friend, philosopher and guide of student. Teacher as a key functionary, he should be able to create and sustain an academic environment. V S Mathur opines –“No system of education, no syllabus , no methodology and no text book can rise above the level of teachers. If a nation wants quality education, it must have quality teachers”.(Dhillon2010) No education program can be successful without proper education of the teachers. Kothari Commission of 1964-66 observed “of all the different factors which influence its quality of education and its contribution to national development, the quality, competence and character of teachers are undoubtedly the most significant. The Commonwealth report explains teacher competency “In order to be competent the teacher must have a knowledge of child development, of the material to be taught and suitable methods , his skill must enable him to teach , advise and guide his pupils, community and culture which he is involved. The need is “to restore integrity, credibility, efficacy and high quality to the teachers skills. ”(NEP 2020) With the growing demand of technology in the 21st century, it becomes crucial for teachers to get acquainted to technology sharpen up their skills. Teachers are to be trained of the new pedagogical strategy and apply it in the classroom situation.

I.I. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study is conducted with the following objectives-

- (a) To study the teaching skills in teaching –learning process.
- (b) To study the teachers competency.
- (c) To study the ICT skills in teaching-learning.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A study of related literature involves locating ,analysing, and evaluating reports of research as well as casual observation and opinions that are related to the study. The related literature forms the foundation upon which all work can be built. One can not develop an insight into the problem to be investigated into unless and until one has learnt what others have done in a particular area of his own interest. The review of related literature helps the author to define the limit of his field.

III. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

For any study proper methodology is very important. It gives the author to plan as per his own way of study and helps the author to complete the writings of his subject. Methodology is called as the blue print of any study. The present study employed descriptive method. It is designed to obtain pertinent and precise information concerning the current status of phenomena. Descriptive study involves description, analysis and interpretation of existing condition.

For the present study, secondary data has been collected from various books, journal, report and E-source.

IV. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Teaching skill is the set of behaviours/ acts of the teacher which facilitates pupils learning . The term ‘skill’ implies efficiency, expertness or proficiency in particular task. Teaching skill therefore, means efficiency or expertness of a teacher to impart a lesson well. The different activities included in the process of teaching such as introduction, motivation, illustration, explanation, closure etc. that help the pupils to comprehend the lesson is known as teaching skills.

According to Singh and Joshi (1990), “ The teaching skill is a set of strictly overt behaviors of the teachers verbal and non-verbal that can be observed ,measured and modified”

In the words of Gage, “Teaching skills are specific instructional activities and procedures that a teacher may use in his classroom. These are to various stages of teaching or in the continuous flow of the teachers performance”.

V. THE TEACHING SKILLS HAVE ESSENTIALLY THREE COMPONENT

1. **Perception:-** Teaching skills have a perceptual component for observing and receiving feedback. The teacher observes and selects appropriate skills to be acquired by him.
2. **Cognition:-** Cognition refers to the behavior or experince of knowing in which there is some degree of awareness, as in thinking and problem solving. Skills are thus cognitive strategies that allow the teachers to complete their assigned task i e teaching learning activities, which they learn through education and training.
3. **Action:-** Teaching skills demand every teacher actually to practice his /her percieved and acquired knowledge in an effective manner in the classroom. This is so because teaching skills are a set of strictly overt and observable behaviors.

While talking of teaching skills, it must be recommended that there is no water tight compartment as regards skills at different stages. These are classified for the sake of convenience , other wise they are interrelated.

1. **Teaching skill at the planning stage-**
 - i) Writing instructional objectives.
 - ii) Selecting the content.
 - iii) Organising the content.
 - iv) Selection of audio-vitual aids and their procurement.
2. **Introductory Stage Skills**
 - i) Creating set induction- preparing the minds of the students.

ii) Introducing the lessons.

3. Presetation Stage skills

i) Questioning skills

- (a) Structuring classroom questions
- (b) Fluency in asking questions
- (c) Probing questions
- (d) Question delivery and distribution
- (e) Higher order questions.

(ii) Presentation skills

- (a) Pacing of lessons
- (b) Lecturing
- (c) Illustrating with examples
- (d) Demonstrating
- (e) Explaining
- (f) Discussing

ii) Audio- visual Aid Skills

- (a) Using teaching aids
- (b) Using blackboard
- (c) Using maps
- (d) Stimulus variation
- (e) Silence and non verbal cues
- (f) Reinforcement

iii) Managerial skills

- (a) Promoting pupil involvement and participation.
- (b) Recognising attending behavior
- (c) Class management

4. Closing Stage Skills

- i) Planned recapitulation
- ii) Evaluating pupil progress
- iii) Diagnosing learning difficulties of the pupils and taking remedial measures.
- iv) Giving assignments.

VI. SEVEN- FOLD CLASSIFICATION OF TECHNICAL SKILLS

An Australian team of authors (Turney et.al 1973) developed a system of classifying teaching skills under which the following seven categories emerged:-

1. **Motivational skills** – Including reinforcing student behavior, varifying the stimulus, set induction, encouraging student involvement, accepting , and supporting student feelings, displaying warmth and enthusiasm recogning and meeting students needs.
2. **Presentation and communication skills**—Including explaining, dramatising, reading, using audio-vitual aids, closure, using silence, encouraging student feedback clarity, pacing and planned repetition.
3. **Questioning skills**—Including refussing and redirecting probing, high level questions, convergent and divergent questions, stimulating student initiative.
4. **Skills of small group and individual instruction**—Organising small group work , developing independent learning, counselling, encouraging cooperative activity and student to student interaction.
5. **Developing student thinking** – Such as fostering inquiry learning , guiding discovery , developing concepts, using stimulation, developing student problem solving skills, make judgements and developing critical thinking.
6. **Evaluative skills**—Including recognising and assessing students progress, diagnosing learning difficulties, providing remedial techniques, self-evaluation and handling evaluative discussions.
7. **Classroom management and discipline**—Including recognising attending and non attending behavior, supervising class group work, encouraging task oriented behavior, giving directions and coping with multiple issues.

VII. TEACHING COMPETENCY

Competency means the right way of conveying units of knowledge, application and skills to the students. The term Teaching Competency refers to the criteria that determine teacher effectiveness. The Dictionary meaning of the term competency is fitness, capacity, suitable or efficiency.

Teaching competency of a teacher refers to the set of knowledge, abilities and beliefs of a teacher possesses and brings to the teaching teaching situation.

The definition of teaching competency considered by many educationist is , competency in planning the lesson, presentation of the lesson, ending or closing the teaching, evaluation of his students capacities, managing the class and maintenance of discipline. Teaching competency is the sum total of all the competencies possessed by the teacher that are used in teaching situation. The teachers' performance in the class is thus dependent on the teachers' competencies. Since the teacher brings about changes in pupils learning using the repertoire of teaching competencies, teacher effectiveness can also be inferred from a measure of teaching competency.

Though teaching competency has been recognised as an important component of teaching –learning process, relatively little effort is made to define the term. A peep –in into the literature of teacher effectiveness as one finds many related terms such as 'teaching success', 'teaching efficiency', 'teacher performance', 'teacher competency' etc.

VIII. DIMENSIONS OF TEACHING COMPETENCY

Out of many dimensions of teaching competency five dimensions are important. They are :-

1. **Planning (pre-instructional)** refer to the selection of objectives, selection of content, organization of content, selection of audio-vitual material. In this we will measure whether the objective of of the lesson were appropriate, clearly stated, relevant to the content, adequate and attainable. Whether the content selected was appropriate, relevant and adequate with respect to the objectives of the lesson and accurate, whether the content selected was properly organised according to logical continuity and psychological organisation. Whether the audio-vitual material chosen were appropriate, suited the pupils and content, adequate and necessary for attaining the objectives.
2. **Presentation (instructional)** refer to introduction of lesson, questioning technique, critical awareness, explanation of concepts and principles, giving appropriate illustration, pupils attention, non-verbal cues, speed of presentation, verbal and non-verbal reinforcement, blackboard work etc. Presentation of lesson include the following : Lesson was introduced effectively and pupils were made ready emotionally and from knowledge point of view to receive the new lesson; continuity in statements or questions, relevance, use of previous knowledge and use of appropriate device and technique.
3. **Closing** refers to appropriateness of closing the lesson and giving proper assignments to the students, which are suitable to individual differences and relevant to content taught.
4. **Evaluation** refers to pupils progress towards the objectives, identification of pupils difficulties in understanding, remedial measures etc. Pupils progress towards the objectives of lesson was checked and the procedures of evaluation were appropriate, relevant to the objectives, valid, reliable and objective.
5. **Managerial** refers to pupils attending and non-attending behaviors, classroom discipline etc. Both attending and non-attending behaviors of pupils were recognized , attending behavior was rewarded, directions were given to eliminate non-attending behavior.

The need and importance of teaching competency may be detailed as follows-

1. Teaching competencies help to improve the quality of teaching –learning process.
2. Teaching competence helps to improve the status of the teachers.
3. Teaching competencies help in the cognitive development of the pupils.
4. Teaching competencies help to personal development of the teachers.

The empirically identified competencies are consolidated and classified under five major categories-

1. **Cognitive based competencies:-** They are content based and help to enlarge the sphere of activities. They define knowledge and intelligence, skills and abilities that expected of a learner.
2. **Performance based competencies;-** The learner demonstrates that he/ she can perform some activity rather than simply being aware of facts. These competencies are skill based and overt action oriented.

3. **Consequence based competencies;-** To demonstrate this competency a person is required to bring a change in others. The achievement of students is a standard measure of consequence based competency.
4. **Affective competency:-** A great emphasis has to be laid on this type of competency rather than the above three categories. The affective competency means the the expected attitudes and values. It is expressed in terms of behaviour.
5. **Exploratory competencies:-** The activities provide opportunity to students to learn, but specific nature of outcome can not be desired. They are also referred as as experience objectives or expressive objectives.

To equip the teachers well in different performance areas, and to enable them to become thoroughly competent to carry out their professional tasks with efficiency and insight, competency areas have been identified. The competency areas are are designed not only simply to provide adequate theoretical and conceptual understanding but also to empower the teachers to perform their responsibilities with professional insight and confidence. To achieve the multiple goals, teacher competencies include relevant conceptual, content, contextual transitional, evaluation aspects.

IX. INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT)

Information and Communication Technologies are an umbrella term that includes all technologies for the manipulation and communication of information. ICTs are the computing and communication facilities and features that variously support teaching, learning and a range of activities in education. ICT has become within a very short time , one of the basic building blocks of modern education. Many countries now regard understanding ICT and mastering the basic skills and concepts of ICT as part of core of education, alongside reading, writing and numeracy. For the purpose of teaching –learning a teacher in modern time follows the ICT in classroom for the betterment of education. Teachers are using E-Mail, whatsapp, virtual mode, flipped classroom, online, video conferencing, social bookmarking and social networking and collaborative learning. Teachers can create social bookmarks of resources chapterwise and invite other teachers to contribute and annotate. The social bookmarks thus created can be shared with the learners and teachers can also give assignments to learners to collaboratively build social bookmarks related to a particular topic. In a rapidly changing world , basic education is essential for an individual be able to access and apply information. Such ability must find include ICTs in the global village. Conventional teaching has emphasized content. Teachers have taught through lectures and presentations interspersed with tutorials and learning activities designed to consolidate and rehearse the content. Contemporary settings now favouring curricula that promote competency and performance. Contemporary ICTs are able to provide strong support for all these requirements and there now many outstanding examples of world class settings for competency and performance based curricula that make sound use of the affordances of these technologies.

Confident teachers are willing to explore new opportunities for changing their classroom practices by using ICT. As a consequence, the use of ICT will not only enhance learning environment but also prepare next generation for future lives and careers. Changed pool of teachers will come changed responsibilities and skill sets for future teaching involving high levels of ICT and need for more facilitative than didactic teaching roles. The use of ICT in educational settings, by itself acts as a catalyst for change in this domain. ICTs by their nature are tools that encourage and support independent learning. Students using ICTs for learning purposes become immersed in the process of learning as more and more students use computers as information sources and cognitive tools.

X. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The above discussion makes it clear that teaching skills are specific instructional activities and that a teacher may use in his classroom. A teacher who has mastered in the skills can perform the duties in a competent way. Presentation and questioning skills of teachers are regarded as the most specific for teaching. Teaching competencies can be identified from various sources. A competency consist of one or more skills. Teaching competency of a teacher can be measured through different means and it can be improved through various techniques. Teaching competencies can be identified from various sources. It has linkage with all the three domains under which performance can be assessed. Various competencies are required for a successful teacher.

REFERENCES

1. Aggarwal, J C. (2004) Teacher and Education in a Developing Society. Vikash Publishing House Pvt. Ltd. Jangpura, New Delhi-110014.

2. Jangaiah, Dr. C & Sabu, Dr. S.(2011)- Teacher Education- A Handbook For Teacher Educator. A.P.H. Publishing Corporation. Ansary Road, Daryaganj, New Delhi-110002.
3. Ali, Dr.Lokman (2015)- Teacher Education. Ashok Publication, Panbazar , Guwahati-1
4. Mate, Jayanta & Roy, Jayashri Chowdhury, Arnab. (2019) - Teacher Education: Modern Period. Kunal Books, Ansary Road, Daryaganj New Delhi-110002.
5. Houston,W R (ed) (1971) Exploring Competency based Education. McCutchan, Berkeley, California.
6. Mac Millan C J B, Nelson T W(eds) (1968) Concepts of Teaching: Philosophical Essays, Rand McNally, Chicago,Illinois.